

DNA of earth as the biggest system of telecommunications for connecting DNAs, dark DNAs and molecules of water on 4+n-dimensional manifold: Exploring the origin of life on the earth

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Abstract:

In this research, we propose a new model for the core of the earth that not only confirms previous results but also gives some new results that are in agreement with observations. In this model, we assume that all DNAs on the earth are imaged on the metal of core and produce DNA-like structure with 10^9 times longer than the core of the earth which is compacted interior of the core. This structure produces a temperature around 6000 K which is in agreement with predicted temperature of the core. Also, this structure is the main cause of the emergence of magnetic field around the earth and gravitational waves for moving around the sun. We show that DNA-like structure of the earth is the biggest system of telecommunications which exchange waves with all DNAs and dark DNAs on eleven dimensional manifold. On four dimensional manifold, DNAs are contracted at least four times around various axes and waves of earth couldnt read their information. However, by adding extra dimensions, the separation distance between particles increases and all of information could be recovered by waves. For this reason, each DNA has two parts which one can be seen on four dimensional universe and another one is existed in extra dimensions and only it's effects can be observed. This extra dark part of DNA called as a dark DNA in extra dimension. Waves of the earth's DNA connect DNAs on four dimensional universe and dark DNAs in extra dimensions and act like topoisomerases in biology. These waves are different for males and females and also different from linear waves which radiate by electronic devices. On the other hand, experiments show that radiated waves of earth interact with molecules of water and store information in their memory. Memory of water is in contradiction with it's chemical

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structure (H_2O). Thus, there should be extra dark DNAs in related to the molecules of water that help them in storing information and exchanging waves with DNAs of earth. This means that molecules of water could have gender like DNAs. On the other hand, earth could emit some special waves to molecules of water and extract DNA-like structure from extra dimensions. This could be the origin of life on the earth. Thus, earth, water and DNA form the best system of telecommunication which control all evolutions of life.

Keywords: Telecommunication, Earth, Dark DNA, Waves

I. INTRODUCTION

One of main question in science is about the relation between the inner core of earth, life, water and waves. Each of these subjects has itself puzzles and all of them together make a more main puzzle. For example, our knowledge about the inner core of earth isnt complete and only limited information has been obtained from the waves of earthquake [1–5]. These considerations have shown that there is equatorial anisotropy in the inner part of Earths inner core [1, 2]. Also, scientists have estimated the temperature of the inner core from the melting temperature of impure iron at the pressure which iron is under at the boundary of the inner core (about 330 GPa) [3]. From these considerations, they have estimated its temperature as between 5,400 K (5,100 C; 9,300 F) and 5,700 K (5,400 C; 9,800 F). However, in 2013 some others have obtained experimentally a substantially higher temperature for the melting point of iron, 6230 [4, 5]. The reason for this high temperature is unclear, however some scientists believe that some nuclear interactions occur interior of the core that are the main cause of high temperature [6–8].

In parallel, the origin of life on the earth and it's relation with evolutions of core is unclear. Also, there are some puzzles about controlling of life by some special dark genes which couldnt be observed and detected by present devices. These genes have been discovered by Hargreaves and his colleagues. They have encountered a dark part of DNA when sequencing the genome of the sand rat (*Psammomys obesus*), a species of gerbil that lives in deserts.

In particular they wanted to study the gerbils genes related to the production of insulin, to understand why this animal is particularly susceptible to type 2 diabetes. But when they looked for a gene called Pdx1 that controls the secretion of insulin, they found it was missing, as were 87 other genes surrounding it. Some of these missing genes, including Pdx1, are essential and without them an animal cannot survive. The first clue was that, in several of the sand rats body tissues, they found the chemical products that the instructions from the missing genes would create. This would only be possible if the genes were present somewhere in the genome, indicating that they werent really missing but just hidden [9]. Now, the question arises that how we can communicate with these special dark DNAs which their effects can be seen, however they are themselves lost.

Another puzzle in sciene is the ability of molecules of water for exchanging information with DNAs and storing their information [10–12]. The chemical structure of water (H_2O) is very simple and has no ability to store information. Thus, how these molecules communicate with other molecules and DNAs. Also, it seems that there is a relation between molecules of water, earth and DNA. Because, water of rain has better effect on the plants and their growth.

In this paper, we will show that earth is the biggest system of telecommunication which exchange waves with DNAs and molecules of water on $4+n$ dimensional manifold. Infact, DNAs of all creatures on the earth are imaged on the metals of the core and produce a DNA-like structure with a long around 10^9 times longer than the core of the earth which is compated interior of the core. This DNA-like structure is the main cause of high temperature of core, magnetic field of earth and gravitational fields which lead to the motion of the earth around the sun. This structure emits some waves that act like topoisomerase in biology and read information of DNAs. These waves are different for males and females and their shape depend on topology of DNAs. However, DNAs are compacted in very small size on four dimensional manifold and their information couldnt be recovered. To solve this problem, some new dimensions are added to manifold of DNAs, the separation distance between bases of DNAs increase and waves of earth can read their information. This means that there are some extra parts of DNAs in extra dimensions which their effects can be observed in evolutions of body. On the other hand, waves of earth and DNAs communicate with molecules of waters and store information in their memory. However, the chemical structure of water couldnt explain the reason for the existence of memory. It seems that there are

some extra DNA-like structures in related to molecules of water which help them to store information and interact with waves of DNAs and earth. As a result, DNA-like structures interior the earth's core, molecules of water and DNAs create the best and biggest system of telecommunications and control all lifes on the earth.

The outline of the paper is as follows. In section II, we show that a DNA-like structure interior of the core may be the cause of emergence of magnetic field, gravitational waves and high temperature. In section III, we show that the core of earth, DNA, waves and molecules of water create the biggest system of telecommunication.

II. EMERGENCE OF MAGNETIC FIELD, GRAVITATIONAL WAVE AND HIGH TEMPERATURE OF EARTH'S CORE BY A DNA-LIKE STRUCTURE

In this section, we will show that all DNAs of creatures are imaged on it's core and produce a DNA-like structure in it (See figure 1). This structure has around 10^9 times longer than the core of the earth and is compacted interior of the core. We will show that this structure is the main cause of gravitational field, magnetic field and high temperature of core.

FIG. 1: Induced DNA-like structure interior of the core by imaging all DNAs on it's metal.

First, we calculate Hamiltonian of one DNA and then, we generalize it to a DNA-like structure. Each DNA is formed from hexagonal and pentagonal molecules (See figure 2). Also, each hexagonal and pentagonal molecule is formed from six or five strings (See figure 3). Thus, we will use of the action of strings for them. [13, 14];

FIG. 2: Each DNA is formed from joining hexagonal and pentagonal molecules.

FIG. 3: Each hexagonal molecule is formed from joining six strings

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + dr^2 + r^2 \left(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2 \right) + \sum_{i=1}^6 dx_i^2 \quad (1)$$

without background fluxes. Here, t is time, r is the radius of page of DNA and θ is the angle of rotation. The action of this DNA can be given by:

FIG. 4: Each DNA and it's hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds are coiled several times around the axis. Topology of DNA has a direct effect on it's radiation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= -T_{tri} \int d^3\sigma \sqrt{\eta^{ab} g_{MN} \partial_a \phi^M \partial_b \phi^N + 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)} \\
 G &= \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{n!} \left(-\frac{F_1 \dots F_n}{\beta^2} \right) \right) \\
 F &= F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \quad F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where g_{MN} is the background metric, $\phi^M(\sigma^a)$'s are scalar fields which are produced by pairing electrons ($\phi = \psi_{up}\psi_{down}$), N is number of exchanged photons between DNAs, σ^a 's are the DNA coordinates, $a, b = 0, 1, \dots, 3$ are world-volume indices of DNA and $M, N = 0, 1, \dots$ are number of paired electrons. Also, G is the nonlinear field and A is the photon which exchanges between DNAs.

Using the metric in equation (1), we can write below relations between coordinates of bulk and a DNA [13, 14]:

$$t(\sigma) = \tau \quad r(\sigma) = \sigma, \quad x_1(\sigma) = z \tag{3}$$

Using above relations, for this DNA in flat space time, the action is given by [13, 14]:

$$S = - \int d\sigma \sigma^2 \sqrt{1 + z'^2 - 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)} \quad (4)$$

For this action, it has been asserted that momentum density is given by [13, 14]:

$$\Pi = \frac{2\pi l_s^2 G'(F) F_{01}}{\sqrt{1 + z'^2 - 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)}} \quad (5)$$

where ' denotes the derivative respect to the field (F). On the other hand, it has been asserted that there is a relation between momentum density and σ [13, 14]:

$$\Pi = \frac{K}{\sigma^2} \quad (6)$$

Using equations (5 and 6) and assuming ($z' \ll G(F)$) and also following method in [13–15], we can obtain :

$$\begin{aligned} H_6 &= \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4 \sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4 \dots \sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4}}}}} } \\ &= \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4}} \right]^6 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} H_5 &= \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4 \sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4 \dots \sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4}}}}} } \\ &= \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma^4}} \right]^5 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Above equation shows that Hamiltonian of bases depend on their shape, separation distance between atoms and angles. Each DNA is coiled several times and thus, its hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds are coiled several times around various axes (See figure 4). Coiling around the axes leads to the motion of electrons in various directions and emergence of magnetic field. Thus, radiation of DNAs depend on their topology and for this reason,

radiation of chromosomes of males are different respect to radiations of chromosomes of females. For coiled hexagonal and pentagonal manifold, we obtain:

$$H_6 = \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma'^4}} \right]^6 = \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta)]^4}} \right]^6 \quad (9)$$

$$H_5 = \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{\sigma'^4}} \right]^5 = \sqrt{1 + z'^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta)]^4}} \right]^5 \quad (10)$$

where, we have used of below relation:

$$\sigma' = z \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta) \quad (11)$$

where θ is the angle which is produced by coiling of manifolds. Above Hamitonians depend on topology of manifolds and angle of their coiling. Now, we should connect all manifolds and produce the Hamiltonian for a DNA. For connecting hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds which are rounded around axes, using Hamiltonians in (9 and 10), we can obtain below Hamiltonian:

$$H_{6-5} = \sqrt{1 + [z'_1]^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z_1 \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta_1)]^4}} \right]^6 \sqrt{1 + [z'_2]^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z_2 \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta_2)]^4}} \right]^5 \times \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[r\phi]^4}} \right] \quad (12)$$

where $\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta$ is the angle between two atoms respect to center of hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds and ϕ is the angle between a hexagonal and a pentagonal manifold. Consequently, Hamiltonian of a DNA can be obtained as:

$$H_{DNA} = \Sigma_{m,n} \sqrt{1 + [z'_1]^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z_1 \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta_1)]^4}} \right]^6 \sqrt{1 + [z'_2]^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z_2 \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta_2)]^4}} \right]^5 \times \dots \times \sqrt{1 + [z'_m]^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z_m \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta_m)]^4}} \right]^6 \sqrt{1 + [z'_n]^2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[z_n \tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta_n)]^4}} \right]^5 \times \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[r_1 \phi_1]^4}} \right] \dots \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[r_n \phi_n]^4}} \right] \quad (13)$$

This Hamiltonian depends on the separation distance and the angle between atoms. Topology of DNA has a direct effect on its energy and for example, energy of DNAs in males and females are different. By using some special values for angles between atoms, we can obtain the known energy of the earth of above Hamiltonian:

$$\begin{aligned}
z_1 &= z_2 \dots = z_n \\
\tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \theta\right) &= n^{\frac{1}{4}} z^{\frac{1}{9}} \\
E_{DNA} &= \Sigma_{m,n} [\sqrt{1 + [z'_1]^2}]^{m+n} [\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[r_1 \phi_1]^4}}] \dots [\sqrt{1 + \frac{K^2}{[r_n \phi_n]^4}}] \left[\frac{1}{nz_1}\right] = \\
GM\left[\frac{1}{R}\right] &
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where

$$R = nz_1 \quad G = K^n \quad M = \Sigma_{m,n} [\sqrt{1 + [z'_1]^2}]^{m+n} \left[\frac{1}{[r_1 \phi_1]}\right] \dots \left[\frac{1}{[r_n \phi_n]}\right] \tag{15}$$

Above equation shows that DNA-like structure interior of the core can produce expected gravitational energy. Thus, this theory is in agreement with known laws of physics. Now, we can assert that magnetic of earth can be obtained by summing over exchanged electromagnetic fields between atoms:

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{earth} &= \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{n!} \left(-\frac{F_1 \dots F_n}{\beta^2}\right)\right) \\
F &= F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \quad F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu \\
B_{earth} &= B_1 + B_2 + \dots + B_n
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where n is the number of magnetic fields between elements of DNA-like structure. Above equation shows that magnetic field of earth can be obtained by summing over magnetic fields of pentagonal and heptagonal manifolds. This magnetic field depends on topology of DNA and for example for a DNA with the gender of male, the magnetic field is different respect to the a DNA with gender of female. Now, we want to obtain temperature of the core. To this aim, we put number of microstates of all pentagonal and hexagonal manifolds equal to number of microstate of DNA-like structure. To calculate number of microstates, we use of normal thermal distribution which is used for Bose-Einstein correlation in statistics:

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{DNA} &= N_{5-6,1}N_{5-6,2}N_{5-6,3}\dots N_{5-6,n} \\
N_{DNA} &= \frac{e^{-\frac{H_{DNA}}{T_{DNA}}}}{1 - e^{-\frac{H_{DNA}}{T_{DNA}}}} \\
N_{5-6} &= \frac{e^{-\frac{H_{5-6}}{T_{5-6}}}}{1 - e^{-\frac{H_{5-6}}{T_{5-6}}}}
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

FIG. 5: Temperature of DNA-like structure in terms of it's size

Consequently, temperature of DNA-like structure or core can be obtained as:

$$T_{core} = T_{DNA-like} = \frac{H_{DNA}}{[e^{\frac{H_{5-6,1}}{T_{5-6,1}}} + 1][1 + e^{\frac{H_{5-6,2}}{T_{5-6,2}}}] \dots [1 + e^{\frac{H_{5-6,n}}{T_{5-6,n}}}]}} \tag{18}$$

This equation shows that temperature of DNA-like structure depends on the Hamiltonian of DNA-like structure, Hamiltonian of hexagonal-pentagonal molecules and temperatures of each manifolds. Assuming that temperatures of hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds be constant and around temperature of room and using equations (12, 13 and 15), we can obtain dependency of temperature in terms of size of core and plot it in figure 5. It is clear that for a DNA-like structure with the size around 10^9 times longer than the core of the earth, temperature will be around 6000 K. This temperature is in agreement with predicted temperature for core. It is concluded that a DNA-like structure with 10^9 meter which is compacted interior of core, can produce all known physics of earth.

III. FORMATION OF A SYSTEM OF TELECOMMUNICATION BY WAVES, DNAs, DARK DNAs AND MOLECULES OF WATER

Now, we consider the process of communications between earth, DNAs and molecules of water. In figure 6, we show that a system like a DNA may be coiled in four dimensions. However, by adding extra strings in extra dimensions, it will be open and its topology will be transferred to a circle. These extra strings may be related to waves or dark DNAs in extra dimensions. We can write below relation between waves, DNAs and dark DNAs in extra dimensions:

FIG. 6: Topology of a system by adding some extra strings in extra dimensions change and shrinks to a circle.

FIG. 7: Dark DNA in extra dimensions.

$$1 = N_{Circle} = N_{DNA}N_{Wave}N_{DarkDNA} \quad (19)$$

FIG. 8: The relation between molecules of water and dark DNAs in extra dimensions.

where N_{Circle} is the number of microstates for a circle which is produced by joining dark DNA, waves and DNA. Also, N_{DNA} is the number of microstates for DNA, $N_{Dark-DNA}$ is the number of microstates for dark DNA and N_{wave} is the number of microstates for waves. This equation shows that waves connect DNAs in four dimensions to dark DNAs in extra dimensions and deform their topology, open their coilings and transferr them to circles (See figure 7). Thus, number of microstates of waves depend on the number of microstates of DNAs and dark DNAs in extra dimensions. We can write below relation for interaction of molecules of water with dark DNAs and waves:

$$1 = N_{Circle} = N_{water}N_{Wave}N_{DarkDNA} \quad (20)$$

where N_{Circle} is the number of microstates for a circle which is produced by joining dark DNA, waves and molecules of water. Also, N_{water} is the number of microstates for molecules of water, $N_{Dark-DNA}$ is the number of microstates for dark DNA and N_{wave} is the number of microstates for waves. Above equation shows that waves connect molecules of water to dark DNAs in extra dimension (See figure 8). For this reason, molecules of water are able to store information, otherwise, the chemical structure of water in four dimension (H_2O) isnt able to store information. This could be a main reason for the existence of memory for molecules of water.

Now, the question arises that what is the origin of 4+ n-dimensional waves. We can show that DNA-like structure of the core is the main cause of production of these waves and their communications with dark DNAs and molecules of water. We can obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
1 &= N_{Circle} \times N_{Circle} \times N_{Circle} = \\
&N_{DNA-like-structure-Earth} N_{Wave} N_{DarkDNA} \times \\
&N_{water} N_{Wave} N_{DarkDNA} \times \\
&N_{water} N_{Wave} N_{DarkDNA}
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Above equation shows that there is a big system of telecommunication which is formed by the core of earth, DNAs, waves, molecules of water and dark DNAs in extra dimension. All evolutions of life on the earth are controlled by this big system of telecommunication. Also, shape of DNAs has a direct effect on their number of microstates and consequently is in relation with number of microstates of waves, molecules of water and dark DNAs in extra dimension.

IV. SOME RESULTS OF THE EXISTENCE OF THE BIGGEST SYSTEM OF TELECOMMUNICATION

We can write below results from our model and calculations: 1. Molecules of water are in related to dark DNAs in extra dimensions. On the other hand, dark DNAs have gender like normal DNAs. Thus, molecules of water can have some properties like gender and each molecule of water with gender of male can attract by DNAs with gender of female and reversely, each molecule of water with gender of female can attract with molecules of water with gender of male (See figures 9 and 10).

2. Equation (19, 20 and 21) give this possibility that number of microstates of molecules of water has a relation with number of microstates of DNAs and dark DNAs. This means that by radiating some waves to molecules of water, we can increase number of microstates of molecules of water and obtain below relation:

$$1 = N_{Circle} N_{water} = N_{water} N_{Wave} N_{DarkDNA} N_{DNA} \tag{22}$$

Above equation shows that by radiating some waves to water, we can extract properties of DNAs. This result is in good agreement with predictions of Montagnier and his colleagues (See figure 11).

FIG. 9: Molecules of water in related to dark DNAs with gender of female.

FIG. 10: Molecules of water in related to dark DNAs with gender of male.

3. DNA-like structure interior of core, DNAs on the earth, dark DNAs in extra dimensions, waves and molecules of water form the best system of telecommunication (See figure 12).

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have shown that earth's core is the biggest system of telecommunication which exchange waves with all DNAs and connect them to dark DNAs in extra dimensions. Infact, imaging of DNAs on the metals interior of core produces a DNA-like structure with around 10^9 times longer than the core of the earth which is compacted and creates an structure similar to chromosomes with size of core. We have shown that this DNA-like structure is the main cause of high temperature of core and magnetic of earth. Also, this

FIG. 11: Emergence of life by waves of the earth in pure water.

FIG. 12: The biggest system of telecommunication from DNA-like structure interior of core, DNAs on the earth, dark DNAs in extra dimensions and molecules of water.

structure produces gravitational fields of earth and leads to the motion of earth around the sun. We have argued that DNA-like structure of earth exchange some non-linear waves with DNAs and recover their information. The shape of these waves depend on topology of DNAs and are different for DNAs of males and females. Each DNA is compacted several times around various axes and reading it's information is hard. However, by adding extra dimensions to four dimensions of universe, the separation distance between elements of DNAs increases and waves of earth could recover their information. Thus, each DNA has an extra dark part in extra dimension which we call them dark DNAs. These extra parts couldnt be observed however their effects can be seen. DNA-like structure of the earth's core exchange waves with both dark and light parts of DNA and connect them. These waves are different for males and females and play the role of topoisomerases in biology. On the

other hand, our calculations and experiments show that these waves interact with molecules of water. However, the chemical structure of water (H_2O) is very simple and can't store any information. This means that there are some extra dark DNAs on 4+n-dimensional manifold which are related to molecules of water and play the role of memory for it. These dark DNAs have gender like other DNAs and give properties of gender to molecules of water. On the other hand, DNA-like structure of the earth could emit some special waves to molecules of water and extract dark DNAs from extra dimensions. This means that the origin of life could be a system of telecommunication which is formed by DNA-like structure interior of the earth, dark DNAs, waves and molecules of water.

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